

An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping on Management of Secondary Schools in Zamfara State

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Abstract

Banditry and kidnapping in secondary schools of Zamfara state is mind blowing, these have become a global issues and threats to school management and administration. Therefore, the paper examines the concepts of banditry and kidnapping, some effects of banditry and kidnapping on management of secondary schools in Zamfara which includes fear and psychological trauma, ineffective school administration, brain drain among others. At the end some recommendations on how to tackle the menace were made such as Counseling psychologists should be prepared and deployed to institutions of learning to rehabilitate students suffering from fear and psychological trauma among others. The paper concludes that for education to continue as a right to every child, government and school management has to provide a safe and favorable teaching and learning environment.

Keywords: Banditry, Kidnapping and school management

Introduction

Nigeria is facing crucial of challenges which are affecting its national growth and development. One of the challenges is the issue of armed banditry and kidnapping on its educational sectors that is threatens the peace of the state and have rampantly contributed to set back in the management and administration of schools in the northwestern Nigeria states. Dahiru (2022) opined that Nigeria has been experiencing, high rate of violence against public schools. Armed banditry, kidnapping of school teachers, learners, and members of school-based local communities, destruction of school infrastructural facilities, *et cetera*; are among the violent activities threatening the sustenance of educational development in the country.

Banditry and kidnapping are among the current societal problems that are negatively affecting the Northern states of Nigeria. Therefore, the pervasive banditry and its associated threats to security, which have enveloped the Northwest region of Nigeria, particularly, Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Sokoto and Niger States, have become a worrisome national security issue of public concern (Olaniyan and Yahaya, 2016). Armed conflicts affect education negatively; they can expose learners to trauma, psychological crises, mental health disorders and physical abuse. Disruption can lead to suspension of classes, which can last for long periods, and schools may end up being used as temporary evacuation centers (NPSSVFS 2021). According to Anka (2017) the acts of banditry and cattle rustling has also limited the chances of many children from accessing basic primary and secondary education as majority of educational structures are either damaged, destroyed or abandoned by people due to constant harassment and fear from both site of the parties.

The current dimension of banditry and kidnapping became worrisome, disheartening and alarming in the Zamfara state when In the early hours of Friday, February 26, 2021, about 279 students (Girls Only School) were kidnapped by armed bandits from their dormitories at Government Girls Secondary School, Jangebe, in Talata Mafara Local Government Area (News Agency of Nigeria, 2021); and in the month of September, 2021, about 73 Students of Government Day Secondary School, Kaya in Maradun Local Government Area of the State (Zamfara State Police Command, 2021; cited by Vanguard News, 2021). A teacher was also among the abductees. Attacks on students and schools are not only reprehensible but a violation of the right of children to an education. It is a right that any society can ill-afford to violate (UNICEF, 2021). This unfortunate circumstance has forced some parents, particularly the well to do, to transfer their children from the school in the Local Government of the State to other states of the federation, while the less privileged had no alternative than to watch their children playing, watching movies, and video games at home, a situation that if unchecked will not augur well for the educational development of the peoples living in the area, which already has been tagged as educationally backward. (Kachallah, Mohammed, Babagana and Musa, et.al, 2021).

Banditry and kidnapping destruct and destabilized the educational activities of the state. The high rate of kidnapping and banditry in certain area of the state has made such area high risk zone for Management of secondary schools in Zamfara State to be effective. The researchers observed that banditry and kidnapping impact negatively on the management of secondary

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schools which may result to, fear and psychological trauma in both staff, parents, and students, poor quality of education, closure of educational institutions, brain drain, destruction of school calendar among others both members of staff and students in the various secondary schools in the affected areas seem to be relocating elsewhere or even if they stay, they constantly live in fear hence managing the schools becomes difficult.

Considering education to be one of the fundamental human right and most of the children attending public schools are of less advantage to go elsewhere and seek for education. The effect of these attacks has further exacerbated the fragile school system which is antithetical to a sustainable national development. Several measures have been implemented to tackle this menace but there are still frequent attacks being experienced in the school environs. If these incessant attacks are not proactively dealt with, it will portend a serious danger to quality of labor force and human capital needed to drive a sustainable economy (Chinedu, Joseph, Chukwuke and Ukwunna, et.al. 2019). The action taken by government and management have deprived a lot of children the right to education because all the boarding schools and schools along the border areas are closed till further notice and this make it difficult for most of the students to attend schools. Therefore, other measures need to be put in place to create a secure and safe environment for teaching and learning. It's in the light of the above that the researcher seeks to examine the effect of banditry and kidnapping on management of secondary schools in Zamfara state.

Concept of Banditry

The term banditry simply means criminal offence that are threatening the safety of the nation. Akinyetun, (2022) refers to banditry as a type of organized crime that includes kidnapping, armed robbery, murder, rape, cattle rustling, and the exploitation of environmental resources. According to Wikipedia.org, Banditry is a type of organized crime committed by outlaws typically involving the threat or use of violence. A person who engages in banditry is known as a bandit and primarily commits crimes such as extortion, robbery, and murder, either as an individual or in groups.

Banditry refers to as the totality of incidences of armed robbery or allied violent crimes, such as kidnapping, cattle rustling, village raids as well as highway raids which involves the use of force, or threat to that effect, to intimidate a person or a group of persons in order to rob, rape, kidnap or kill the victims (Olafeju and Peter, 2021). However, Uche and Iwuamadi, (2018) state that banditry is reflected in criminal escapades like cattle rustling, kidnapping, armed robbery, drug abuse, arson, rape and the brazen and gruesome massacre of people of agrarian communities with sophisticated weapons by suspected herdsmen and reprisal attacks from surviving victims, a development that has been brought to the front burner of national security. In addition, Kangyang and Aipe (2021) opine that banditry encompasses a range of criminal activity allied to various non-ethnic and ethnic factors, many of the recent large scale armed attacks are suspected to have been carried out by Fulani assailants.

Concept of Kidnapping

Kidnapping as defined by various authors simply means to abduct, capture, carry off, remove or steal away a person (Ogabido 2009). According to Asuquo (2009) the term "kidnapping" is difficult and complex to define with precision, because it varies from State to State scenario as well as jurisdiction to jurisdiction. In any case, it is seen as the forceful seizure, taking away and unlawful detention of a person against his/her will. It is a common law offence and the key part is that, it is an unwanted act on the part of the victim. It is a restriction of someone else's liberty which violates the provision of freedom of movement as enshrined in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, where every other law takes its cue from. For this reason, Inyang and Abraham (2013) defined it as the forcible seizure, taking away and unlawful detention of a person against his/her will. It is a common law offence and the key part is that it is unwanted act on the part of the victim.

Kidnapping can be defined as the act of seizing and detaining or carrying away a person's by unlawful force or by fraud and often with a demand for ransom, for an act to be deemed Kidnapping, it must involve coercive movement of a victim from one place to another detention or seizure of that person be it a child or an adult (Eyikomisan, Ochigbo and Beetseh, 2021). Thus, Kidnapping is the act of holding a person captive in order to make them offer something in return for their release. The motivation may be economic, political, or ideological. He states that there is different pattern of kidnapping, among them are kidnap for ransom, kidnap for ritual, kidnap for strategic bargain, and child abduction (Okoli, 2022). In addition, Ibrahim and Muktar 2017 view that kidnapping is usually motivated by financial gain or political benefit. Thus, opportunist or traditional criminals as well as political dissidents can resort to kidnapping in order to illegally obtain economic gains or have their demands granted. Therefore, the act of kidnapping may include snatching, capturing seizing and abduct a person in order to collect a ransom in return or settle some disagreement among people.

Effect of banditry and kidnapping on management of secondary schools in Zamfara State

The act of banditry and kidnapping affect the lives of many Nigeria more especially those victims living in various community of Zamfara state, which also affect the number of schools located in such areas. The effects of banditry and kidnapping on management and administration of secondary schools in Nigerian educational institutions include fear and psychological trauma, ineffective school administration, poor quality of education, disruption of academic calendar, brain drain, and closure of educational institutions.

1. Fear and Psychological trauma

In a society where the rate of banditry and kidnapping is high, people will be affected with a lot of fear and psychological trauma. The insurgent activities have injected fear into the minds of many parents and created psychological trauma among the students (Kilcullen, 2006; Metz, 2007; Paul, Clarke & Grill, 2011; Murtada, 2013). Attacks on schools in Zamfara is discouraging parents and students from going to schools especially in the areas affected. Many parents due to fear have decided to keep their children at home instead of been killed and kidnapped at schools where safety is not guaranteed. The students may not go to school due to fear of been kidnapped even if they go they will find it difficult to pay attention and concentrate in the classroom or school activities. Fear produced by banditry and kidnapping interferes with effective learning and constitutes a hitch to academic success and creates unstable behaviour among students. Most of school administrator's teachers, principal and vice have the fear of going to schools that are located in the affected areas which may cause anxiety and traumatic. The traumatic experience that the victims of kidnapping and banditry undergo usually leaves an indelible mark on them that last a life time. This has a negative psychological effect, especially in children and in most cases leads to depression, anxiety and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) which unfortunately has a long lasting effect (Chukwueme, et al., 2019)

2. Ineffective School administration

One of the objectives of schools' administration is to secure the live and property of its people. School administrators also provide healthy and conducive atmosphere for teaching, learning, experiment and research. Arockiasamy (2017) opined that school administration is not merely set of rules, regulations of orders to be followed by all concerned. It is humane, flexible, constructive, result oriented and goal oriented. It is not one-man show. This implies that School administration involves managing, administering the curriculum and teaching, pastoral care, discipline, assessment, evaluation and examinations, resources allocation, costing and forward planning, staff appraisal relationship with the community, use of practical skills necessary for surveying the policies of organization such as decision-making, negotiation, bargaining, communication, conflict handling, running meetings and so on (Okereke, 2008).

The insecurity in the Northern Nigeria has led to disruption of school administration (Ogunode & Kolo 2021). They also observed that school administration deals with the internal supervision of teaching and learning programme. It implies the coordination of all human and materials resources within the schools for the implementation of the schools programme for the realization of the objectives of the schools. The effect of banditry and kidnapping in the region have led to suspension of school programme such as school monitoring, supervision and inspection, teaching and learning, execution programme, examination and sport and all other gathering activities. School administrators were unable to go to school's inspection and teachers' activities were disrupted which affect the improvement of educational system.

3. Poor Quality of Education

Children have a right to education, a quality education which among them includes: environments that are healthy, safe, protective and gender-sensitive (UNICEF, 2000). Insecurity in Nigeria is contributing to poor quality education because, school scheme of work and syllables are not covered in most educational institutions due to school closed down. Many educational institutions in the country are always been closed down due to insecurity. The inability of these educational institutions to cover their scheme of work and syllables is reducing the quality of education (Ogunode, et.al. 2021). The entire educational institutions in Zamfara State were closed down because of attacked by bandit and kidnapper, many students were forced to go home and teaching and learning stopped and on resumption, the students were asked to start their examinations without revision or continuation of the term. Insurgency, forces students to graduate without completion of scheme of work and move others from one form of class to another class without covering the stipulated scheme of work for the time due to school closure, as a result of attacked. Schools are not able to spend stipulated number of months per term. Schools in unsafe areas lack adequate qualified teachers. As such, students are not properly taught (Oluyomi, & Grace, 2016). Paul (2015) submitted that the graduates produced through insecurity end up not having the requisite knowledge and skill to operate in the workplace; they rather become a liability. The ultimate effect is poor performance of organizations and hence the national economy. This could be one of the greatest problems facing the Nigerian economy today since the incidences of insecurity in the educational system are quite high

4. Disruptions of Academic Calendar

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The academic calendar of secondary schools in Zamfara has been affected by the insurgency challenges. Jacob and Ndubuisi (2021) observed that educational institutions operate on planned academic calendar which specifies the academic session, terms and weeks that school will open for teaching and learning. Scheme of work and syllables are there to be covered within the school calendar. These academic calendar and programmes of educational institutions are poorly implemented due to closure of school which is unhealthy for the development of education because, teaching and learning and other academic activities are intermittently disrupted. The government had shut down all the schools in Zamfara state both private and public for almost a term thousand students and pupils are at home after the incidence of GGSS Jangebe was school students' kidnap. Schools write first term, second term and term internal examinations. Some of these internal exams across the region have been disrupted. Most of the final year students are unable to cover their syllabus and scheme of work and they sat for the secondary schools leaving certificate, without considering the effects on management and learner's academic performance which disrupt the academic calendar.

5. Brain-Drains

The management of education in Nigeria depends on the effectiveness of professional administrators, teachers and non-teaching staff available to carry out the educational activities or services within the school. The act of banditry and kidnapping in Zamfara is affecting the management of secondary school education because most of the teachers are leaving the teaching profession since most of the schools are not secure and conducive for teaching and learning to take place due to this problem mass movement of professional teachers from one state to another leaving many educational institutions without qualified teachers. Many teachers are resigning their appointment due to insurgency in state and fitting on in other state or other profession that is safe. According to Ogunode, et.al. 2021 the implication of this mass migration of teachers from this region is that, less teachers will be available to teach and this will affect the quality of education because, there will be inadequate professional teachers to attend to the students.

Closures of Educational Institutions

Management of educational institution cannot be achieved in an empty space. This implies that noble goal of education can never be achieved in a vacuum. They would be achieved in a conducive and peaceful school environment. If there is a feeling of insecurity within and outside the school environment, both students and teachers are likely to be deterred and this inhibits academic performance of the students. Attacks on secondary schools in Nigeria have led many states government order closure of all educational institutions in their states to prevent further attacks (Lehr, 2004). More states in Northern Nigeria have ordered all schools to close following kidnapping of hundreds of pupils in Katsina State as reported by (BB.C, 2020). Zamfara state government ordered the closure of ten (10) secondary schools across the border line of Zamfara with Katsina state in bid to prevent the abduction of students by armed bandits until security situation improves. The affected schools were Government secondary school Zurmi, Government secondary school Birnin Magagi, Government Arabic secondary school Shinkafi, Science secondary school Shinkafi, Science secondary school Dansadau, Science secondary school Bukkuyum, Government Day secondary schools Nasarawa Mailayi, Government Day secondary school Gusami and Government Day secondary school Gurbin Bore. All the principal of the affected schools has been directed to ensure immediate closure of the affected school which greatly affect the management and administrations of all the affected schools as a result of this, most students have to move to other places to pursue education which will affect the quality of education.

On Friday 26, February 2021 Government girls' secondary school Jangebe was attacked by armed bandit and about 276 were abducted or kidnap following this abduction the governor ordered the immediate closure of all the boarding secondary schools in the state until date. This abduction really shocks the government, management, parents and students. This attacked created an unstable learning environment, discouraged parents from sending their children to school more especially the Girl-child. The girl-child is also negatively affected. She is kept at home for a long time or given out for early marriage (Oluyomi, & Grace, 2016). Zamfara state has on September, 2021 ordered the closure of all the schools within the state, both primary and secondary schools following Wednesday 1 September, 2021 abduction of 73 students and a teacher from public school in the state. The schools were closed for 4months, the schools resume on 17 January, 2022 this has really disrupted the academic school calendar and student's education on resumption not all the schools are resume. The private and public schools that were categorized as green and yellow by the ministry should resume normal activities while schools in the red category remain closed until the security situation improves. Nnamdi (2021) observed that the attacks could curtail attendance once schools reopen. Already, many parents say they no longer consider schools safe. Many Muslim parents in the North West are skeptical of what they perceive as a Western model of education; it is likely that some won't allow their children to return. Moreover, given the wider insecurity in the region, the abductions could prompt teachers and other staff to quit and look for employment

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elsewhere. Many students have been displaced and kept out of school as submitted by (Gustafsson-Wright, & Smith, 2014; Nwachukwu, et.al. 2015).

Conclusions

The school as a centered of attention is becoming more difficult to handle by school management due to banditry and kidnapping attacked on schools and community which instill fear and trauma in the lives of the school management, students and staff, disruption of school calendar, poor quality of education, closure of schools among others. Therefore, for education to continue as a right to every child government and the school management has to provide a safe and favorable environment through the following deployed counseling psychologists to all educational institutions, installed modern technology to monitored all schools, improve administrators and teacher's quality of work life, proving of security guards to safe guard life and property of all educational institutions among others. Therefore, successful management of schools depends on the security situation of the environment, security of teachers and students as well as the security of the school administrators.

Recommendations

To solve the identified problems, the following are recommended: -

- 1 Counseling psychologists should be prepared and deployed to institutions of learning to rehabilitate students suffering from fear and psychological trauma. Counselors should be able to adopt various strategies among include the use Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy to alleviate stress, fear, and anxiety, psychological disturbance that both the teachers and students face as a result of the activities of insurgency.
- 2 Government should liaise with the school management to develop strategies that will improve the security and safety of teachers and learners in educational institution. The school administrators and teachers should be sensitized to ensure that once children are in school, they have to be monitor to prevent them from loitering outside the school and to also be watchful to know the kind of visitors that come to the schools not everyone should be allowed into the educational institution. Installation of modern technology like CCTV will help to improve the security condition. Therefore, safety learning and teaching environment encourage teamwork between management and teachers as well as effect school programme will be executed. This would encourage the school administrator to discharge their responsibilities of monitoring, supervision, inspection among others effectively and efficiently.
- 3 The government and school management should encourage teachers to engage in an advocacy campaign to provide online training or through the media training to educate students when at home so that whenever school resumes not all will be forgotten. Other programme should be initiated by the government to teach those students at home in a safe and secure place in different community by some educational aspect before school resumed in order to improve quality education.
- 4 Government and school management create awareness regarding security and safety for learners and its implication. This can be done through sensitization and enlightenment campaign through newspapers, radio, television and social media handles so that parents will be aware of why some of the schools in their community are closed down and will not be open, that there are certain criteria approved and recognized only those schools that meet the minimum standards in safety and security requirement will be open. That is why the government and school management open schools with green and yellow and closed all in red zones.

References

- Akinyetun, T S (2022) Banditry in Nigeria insights from situational action and situational crime prevention theories. Retrived from <https://www.acCORD.org.za>bandit>. Sagejournal. Research Article on August 08 2022
- Anka, A.S. (2017). Emerging issues in Zamfara armed banditry and cattle rustling: Collapse of the peace deal and resurgence of fresh violence. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 6(12). Dissertation, Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Uyo, Nigeria
- Arockiasamy, S. (2017) School Management. Elective-school-management-drarock-pdf. <https://drarockiasamy.wordpress.com> Retrieved on August, 24 2022
- Asuquo, M. E. (2009), *The Upsurge of Kidnapping and Its Influence on Public Order in Akwa Ibom State*. Term Paper presented in the Department of Sociology/Anthropology, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State- Nigeria.
- BBC (2020) Nigerian states close schools after students kidnapped in Katsina <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-55338785>

An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping... (Abubakar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367092>

- Chinedu, N., Joseph, U., Chukwuka, A., & Ukwunna, G.C. (2019). Insecurity and the Nigeria School System: The Securitization Option for Sustainable Development. *The 2nd International Conference of Unizik Business School, Nigeria*.
- Dahiru, A. S. (2021), The Role of Education Stakeholders towards achieving a Safe School Environment: Implications on Educational Development. Nigeria Union of Teachers.
- Eyikomisan H. A, Ochigbo, S. E & Beetseh, H. (2021), The Perceived Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping on National Development in Nigeria in Ochigbo, Beetseh, and Abubakar ed. *Global insecurities; challenges and the way forward* 1st ed. Akure: Science and Education Development Inst; Nigeria P. 92-98
- Gustafsson-Wright, E., & Smith, K. (2014). Abducting school girls in Nigeria: Improving education and preventing future book haram attacks, *Education & development*. Retrieved from <http://www.brookingsedu/blogs/education-plus-development/post/2014/17/-nigeriaeducation-learning-boko-haram-gustafsson-wright>
- Ibrahim B & Mukhtar J I (2017) An Analysis of the Causes and Consequences of Kidnapping in Nigeria. *An international multi-disciplinary journal, bahir dar, ethiopia afrrev* 11 (4), P134-143
- Inyang J.D & Abraham, U. (2013), The Social Problem of Kidnapping and its implications on the Socio-Economic Development of Nigeria. A study of Uyo Metropolis: *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 4(6), 531-544.
- Jacob, O. N & Ndubuisi, A. G (2021), The Effects of Incessant Closure of Schools on School Administration in Northern Nigeria. *International journal f development and public policy*,1(5) Retrived from <https://openaccessjournals.eu/index.php/ijiaet/article/view/261/255> on August, 22 2022
- Kachallah R, Mohammed B.B. Babagana U. U & Musa S. (2021), Impact of Insurgency on Management of Senior Secondary Schools in Potiskum Local Government Area, Yobe state, Nigeria: *Implication for Counselling International Journal of Research in Education and Sustainable Development* 1, (10) P. 116
- Kangyang J.P & Aipe A. M (2021) Hardsmen, Banditry and Kidnapping activities: A threat to Secondary School in Nigeria in Ochigbo, Beetseh, and Abubakar ed. *Global Insecurities: Challenges and the way forward*. 1st ed. Akure, Science and Education Development inst. Nigeria, P.82-91
- Kilcullen, D. (2006). Counter-Insurgency. *Survival: The IISS Quarterly Report*. Redux. Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Table for determining sample size of a known population.
- Lehr, (2004), Positive School Climate Information for Education, National Association of School Psychologists, Retrieved on August, 11, 2022 from <https://www.nasponline.org/school-climate-hops>
- Metz, S. (2007). Rethinking Insurgency.US Government Publication.Retrieved from <http://www.StrategicStudiesInstitute.army.mil/>.
- Murtada, A. (2013). Boko Haram in Nigeria: Its Beginnings, Principles and Activities in Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://www.salafricanhaj.com>
- Nnamdi, O, (2021), Halting Repeated School Kidnappings in Nigeria <https://www.crisisgroup.org/africa/west-africa/nigeria/halting-repeated-school-kidnappings> Niger
- NPSSVFS (2021) National Policy on Safety, Security and Violence-Free School with its implementing Guidelines. Nigeria Education in emergencies working group. Nigeria <https://www.humanitarianresponse.info/en/operations/nigeria/education-p.1-91>
- Nwachukwu, K.J., Abdullahi, U., & Kyari, Y.B. (2015). Use of defense mechanism in coping with psychological stress among insurgency displaced adolescents in Maiduguri. *The Nigerian Educational Psychologist*, 13 (1), 197-203.
- Ogabido, G. O. (2009), *Kidnapping: New Brand of Terrorism*. Saturday Sun, October 31. P.7-2.
- Ogunode N. J. & Kolo, F (2021), Effects of Insecurity on Basic education administration in Northern Nigeria. *International Journal of Discovers and innovation in applied sciences* 1(7), 1-8
- Ogunode, N, J. Ahaotu G. N. & Obi-E, U. (2021), Effects of Insecurity on School Administration in Nigeria. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, (13). P:94-102
- Okereke, C. (2008), Quality Assurance in Teacher selection among Private Secondary Schools in Owerri Municipal, Imo State for Effective Implementation of UBE. *Journal of curriculum organization for Nigeria* P. 34-44
- Okoli A.C (2021), Of Banditry and Human Rustling: The Scourge of Kidnapping in Northern Nigeria *Africa Journal on Terrorism* P.209-222
- Okoli, A. C (2022), who's at Risk of being kidnapped in Nigeria? The Conversation. Retrieved from <https://theconversation.com> on August-08-2022
- Olaniyan, A. & Yahaya, A. (2016). Cows, bandits, and violent conflicts: Understanding cattle rustling in northern Nigeria. *Africa Spectrum*, 51(3), 93-105.

An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping... (Abubakar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367092>

- Olapeju R. M & Peter A. O. (2021), The Impact of Banditry on Nigeria's Security in the Fourth Republic: An Evaluation of Nigeria's Northwest p 1-6
- Oluyomi A, & Grace S.,M, (2016) *Environmental Insecurity and the Nigerian Child's Learning: Coping Strategies Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol. 4, No.1, P 13-17
- Paul N, (2015) The Effect of Insecurity on Quality Tertiary Education in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Applied Sciences*, 3(6) P 965-976
- Paul, C., Clarke, C. P., and Grill, B. (2011). Victory Has a Thousand Fathers: Evidence of Effective Approaches to Counterinsurgency, 1978-2008. *Small Wars Journal*. Retrieved from <http://www.smallwarsjournal.com>.
- Uche, J. C. & Iwuamadi, C. K. (2018). Nigeria: Rural banditry and community resilience in the Nimbo community. *Conflict Studies Quarterly*, (24), 71-82.
- UNICEF. (2021). "Statement from Peter Hawkins, UNICEF Nigeria Representative, on another school attack in Zamfara State, north-west Nigeria". Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/press-releases/statement-peter-hawkins-unicef-nigeria-representative-another-school-attack-zamfara>. Accessed on August, 10, 2021.
- Vanguard News. (2021). "Police Confirm Abduction of 73 Zamfara Students. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2021/09/police-confirm-abduction-of-73-zamfara-students/amp/>. Accessed on August, 8, 2022.